

ENGLISH LANGUAGE SYSTEMS AND PROBLEMS IN TEACHING THEM

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ABSTRACT

Theoretical conclusions and sources presented in this work analysis of the forms of linguistic aspects and approach to their teaching; based on the analysis of the problems faced by teachers and students, a comparison of English and Uzbek modern methods and means of solving problems allows you to get information about the specification. The materials collected on the topic can be used as resources when taking special courses at the philological faculties of higher educational institutions, seminars and seminars on methodology, introduction to linguistics, integrated learning, integrated foreign language course.

Introduction

Teaching the English language to non-English speakers is not an easy job for the teachers. The quality of a good teacher is to recognize the problems and facilitate the best ever environments for the students and encourage them to learn. Now in this chapter we are going to discuss all the problems faced by teachers in teaching the English language systems.

According to Richards, "any satisfactory model of language development must be compatible with how learners learn; their ability to perceive, conceptualize, store, and access information; and their motivations". The question of how language learning is related to developmental psychology, then, might be, "Do learners learn language in the same way they learn other things, such as how to tie their shoes or how to build with

blocks, or do learners have a special cognitive capacity for language learning?" Much of the research in child language acquisition has focused on the early language that learners produce. Since researchers can't directly observe what goes on in the brain, and since they can't ask one- or two-year-olds to reflect on how they are learning language, scientists have to rely on learners' linguistic output [53.23p].

Researchers who have observed learners over time and have transcribed learners' speech have identified certain stages in normal language development. This work is very intensive, and the studies are longitudinal. We describe several key research studies that have looked at child language development. Brown, for example, studied three learners over time. He found

that their earliest utterances referred to things of interest to the learners.

Methods

Knowledge of linguistics is the basis for pedagogical language knowledge, an understanding of how to meet the language demands of the academic content subjects. All this depends upon the ability and level of understanding and interest of the learners. There is no sure fire remedy or method to enhance comprehension of second language system in a day or two. As it was explained earlier in our findings students' vocabulary bank can be enriched on a gradual basis and one should always show keen interest and enthusiasm in finding, learning and understanding the language have concluded, teaching students learning skills can encompass strategies that use the different types of instruction in creating word context, content, meaning and application that will prove beneficial and powerful as the student grows to understand the importance and application of units and understanding a huge selection of them makes communication a lot easier to navigate. Through using the four main skills of speaking, reading, writing and listening, comprehension of language systems expands and strengthens.

The population of the study consists of 100 students and 15 teachers from the school № 1 and 20 students as well as 3 teachers of "Special one" linguistic course center in Bukhara, while the study sample is comprised of 125 students and 18 teachers. The findings obtained from the study are

the following: 1- According to the students, "teachers' getting stuck on explaining grammar rules" is the highest factor encountered in English learning and teaching while "teachers' having difficulty in vocabulary or to be exact teaching new topic based lexicons " is the lowest factor. 2- As grade levels and the number of siblings increase, the students' perceptions on the problems encountered in English teaching and learning also rise. 3- There are no significant differences between the students' opinions on the problems encountered in English teaching and learning according to abilities and skills, applied tools and techniques variables.

With this study, it is aimed to put forward the problems encountered in English teaching-learning processes according to secondary school students. In accordance with this main purpose, the problems encountered in English teaching learning according to secondary school students were examined in terms of the variables as gender, grade level, number of siblings, type of school, parents occupation, family income level, taking/or not refresher course, the place and the duration of the course.

Results

Problems Encountered in English Teaching and Learning Survey, which was developed by Ergüder and used as the data collection tool in the study, adapted by being protected largely and finalized by being received on expert opinions. As the result of reliability analysis of the survey,

No		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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1.	I have difficulty in understanding what to read in English	12,5	75,6	10,2	5,9	3,2
2.	I have difficulty in understanding what to listen in English.	81,94	1,75	5,1	1,5	2,8
3.	I have difficulty in speaking English.	2,77	78,4	3,8	10,6	5,4
4.	I have difficulty in getting my thoughts in writing in English.	1,38	65,4	21,3	16,1	4,8
5.	I have difficulty in learning the grammar of English.	5,4	14,9	54,2	17,3	10,5
6.	That Uzbek and English grammar rules do not resemble each other hinders me to learn English.	55,65	31,2	11,7	-	-
7.	I do not have enough written resources in foreign language.	-	32,8	25,6	32,9	11,5
8.	Grammar is being intensively processed in our English class	1,5	16,8	49,2	28,6	14,5
9.	Our teacher does not make speech activities in lesson.	1,38	65,4	21,3	6,1	14,8
10.	Our teacher does not process listening texts in the lesson.	11,39	55,4	11,3	16,1	3,8

Figure 1.1 The Percent and Means of the Responses of the Survey Items Given by the Secondary School Students

Within its aims to state the secondary school students' opinions about the problems encountered in English teaching-learning processes, the students see the "teachers' getting angry at mistakes" as the most important factor which affect negatively English learning and teaching while they see the "teachers' not being prepared for lessons" as the lowest factor. It can be said that these answers about the reasons for failure in English learning and teaching overlap with some other research results in the literature. This situation shows that foreign language teaching-learning processes are not only cognitive-based, but also associated with affective domain. Therefore it can be said that teaching-learning process should be organized in this context. The students show mostly the lack of subsidiary course materials and having difficulty in

understanding what to read in English as the other problems encountered in the English language learning and teaching. This finding overlaps with the other research results in the literature.

According to Table 1.1, when examined the means of the responses of the survey items given by the students, it is seen that the 2nd item "I have difficulty in understanding what to listen in English" has the highest mean. According to Table 1, the most negative items which affect English learning and teaching according to the students are respectively as following from highest to lowest: the 5th item "I have difficulty in getting my thoughts in writing in English". the 1st item "I have difficulty in understanding what I read English"; the 3rd item "I have difficulty in speaking English"; the 8th item "Grammar is being intensively processed in our English class"; the 2nd item

“I have difficulty in understanding what I listen to English”; the 4th item “I have difficulty in getting my thoughts in writing in English; the 5th item “I have difficulty in learning the grammar rule of English”.

According to Table 1.2 , when examined the means of the responses of the survey items given by the students, it is seen that the “I have difficulty in understanding what to listen in English” has the lowest mean.

No		Always	Sometimes	Never
1.	I use learners' L1 to teach new vocabulary.	80,94	19,06	-
2.	I employ learners' L1 to explain grammar.	77,77	22,23	-
3.	I use learners' L1 to provide clarification when learners do not understand in L2.	62,5	34,73	2,77
4.	I use learners' L1 to provide feedback and explain their errors.	81,94	16,98	1,38
5.	I use learners' L1 in giving written corrective feedback on learners' compositions.	6,94	31,95	61,11
6.	I use learners' L1 to explain instructions for assignments or projects.	8,33	26,4	65,27
7.	I use learners' L1 to give meta-linguistic knowledge, in particular about discussing the tasks, such as the objective and the steps of tasks.	29,16	47,23	23,61
8.	I use learners' L1 to negotiate the syllabus and the lesson.	29,16	56,96	13,88
9.	I use learners' L1 in administrative issues like exam announcement.	19,44	37,51	43,05
10.	I use learners' L1 in dealing with discipline problems in class.	54.16	45.84	-
11.	I use learners' L1 to establish or assert authority. I us I use learners' L1 at the end of the class to answer possible questions.	13.88	45.85	40.27
12.	I use learners' L1 to encourage and com fort learners.	49.44	35.29	15.27
13.	I use learners' L1 to build rapport with learners.	12.5	22.23	65.27
14.	I use learners' L1 in giving personal comments.	69.44	26.4	4.16
15.	I use A. V. aids beneficially in the teaching of English grammar and vocabulary	43.05	16.68	40.27
16.	I use learners' L1 in presenting information about the target culture, in particular discussing cross-cultural issues.	49.44	38.06	12.5
17.	I take advantage of learners' L1 to supervise and guide them when they perform a task collaboratively.	13.88	45.85	40.27

18.	I employ learners' L1 to conduct pre-task activities, namely pre-listening and pre-reading.	49.44	35.29	15.27
19.	I use learners' L1 in giving individual help to learners.	12.5	22.23	65.27

Figure 1.2 The percentage of answers to the items of the questionnaire

Furthermore, 19 respondents having the view that they try to speak as much as possible in English to the secondary school students to some extent.

In item 1 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to teach new vocabulary." The mean score 19.06 and standard deviation 80.94 for the above statement shows majority of the respondents (87) have the view that they use their L1 in explanation of vocabulary to secondary school students in their school.

In item 2 the statement is, "I employ learners' L1 to explain grammar" The mean score 77.77 and standard deviation 22.23 for the above statement shows majority of the respondents (94) have the opinion that English teachers must use L1 in grammar teaching.

In item 3 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to provide clarification when learners do not understand in L2." The mean score 34.73 and standard deviation 62.5 show majority of the respondents (109) are not sure that English teachers should use their L1. In spite of this, English teachers have the opinion that they are trained in the subject of English to some extent.

In item 4 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to provide feedback and explain their errors." The mean score 1.38 and standard deviation 81.94 for the above statement reveals majority of the respondents (98) show that feedbacks to students are not so common while 37 secondary school English teachers have the view that they provide them during the classes.

In item 5 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 in giving written corrective feedback on learners' compositions." The mean score 6.94 and standard deviation 61.11 display majority of the respondents (85) have view that teachers try to understand written compositions of students to give clear feedback.

In item 6 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to explain instructions for assignments or projects." The mean score 8.33 and standard deviation 65.27 show majority of the English teachers' (78) having the view that they know about the methodology of teaching English about showing right track of doing the tasks.

In item 7 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to give meta-linguistic knowledge, in particular about discussing the tasks, such as the objective and the steps of tasks" The mean score 23.61 and standard deviation 47.23 reveals the majority of the respondents (50) responded that they know about the cognitive method because mostly they teach through meta linguistic techniques in the English class.

In item 8 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to negotiate the syllabus and the lesson" The mean score 2.77 and standard deviation 0.57 indicate majority of the English teachers (130) responded to the statement that they use L1 to negotiate syllabus in the class.

In item 9 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 in administrative issues like exam announcement." The mean score 13.88 and standard deviation 56.96 for the above

statement shows that majority of the respondents (72) are in response to announcements and use L1 to declare them.

In item 11 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to encourage and comfort learners" The mean score 2.43 and standard deviation 0.81 for the above statement shows that majority of the respondents (98) responded; they are main facilitators of the lesson.

In item 12 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 to build rapport with learners" The mean score 1.56 and standard deviation 0.64 show majority of the respondents (79) responded that they do not use audio lingual method of teaching but English teachers (58) have the view that they seldom use L1 to build a good rapport to some extent in the English class.

In item 14 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 in giving personal comments" The mean score 1.46 and standard deviation 0.64 indicate majority of the respondents (93) are in the favor that they do not use L1 to comment secondary school students.

In item 15 the statement is, "I use A. V. aids to explain the topic" The mean score 2.81 and standard deviation 0.56 for the above statement reveals majority of the respondents (135) think that audio visual aids are beneficial in the teaching of English grammar.

In item 16 the statement is, "I use A. V. aids beneficially in the teaching of English grammar and vocabulary" The mean score 1.42 and standard deviation 0.56 for the above mention statement indicate majority of the respondents (91) have view that they do not use audio visual aids to teaching English grammar and vocabulary to secondary school student while English teachers (53) responded that they use audio visual aids to teach English grammar to

some extent to the secondary school students.

In item 17 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 in presenting information about the target culture, in particular discussing cross-cultural issues" The mean score 2.91 and standard deviation 0.38 for the above statement indicate almost all the respondents (142) having the view that they are teaching English through discussion classes.

In item 18 the statement is, "I take advantage of learners' L1 to supervise and guide them when they perform a task collaboratively" The mean score 2.83 and standard deviation 0.51 for the above statement shows majority of the respondents (136) responded that they think overcrowded classes affect the teaching of English grammar in the classrooms.

In item 19 the statement is, "I employ learners' L1 to conduct pre-task activities, namely pre-listening and pre-reading." For the above statement, the mean score 2.16 and standard deviation 0.51 indicate majority of the respondents (106) responded that they are to some extent satisfied with the English textbooks at secondary level as they provide such tasks.

In item 20 the statement is, "I use learners' L1 in giving individual help to learners" The mean score 2.37 and standard deviation 0.72 for the statement shows majority of the respondents (80) responded that it is not an easy task to teach the secondary school students.

Improper use of these structures in a complex sentence leads to a violation of the logic of the statement and, as a consequence, the failure of communication tasks. In this regard, we see the need for more detailed equipment of this topic and

the development of appropriate recommendations. Another obstacle on the way to solving the communicative problem of linguistics is the correct perception of the said form, that is, the perception of what is said by ear. The next problem is the translation of the form into the General meaning. At this stage, it is important that the listener knows at least one, the most General meaning of the word that has been said to others. Therefore, when teaching English as a means of communication, it is important to make it clear to students that a person perceives what is said through his individual and cultural prism, and therefore, it is necessary to convey as accurately as possible all the meanings that the word carries.

The transition from cultural significance to the individual is manifested in the projection of cultural significance through the prism of some of its own properties, attitudes. This barrier in communication, which is called psychological, and is the most difficult to overcome in communication between individuals, because all people have a mechanism of "encryption" and "decryption" is different and depends on different reasons, one of which is a different psychology of people. Therefore, the relevance of the communicative problem has now acquired unprecedented acuteness. This problem is also related to one of the problems of translation theory, namely the methods of transmission without equivalent vocabulary, i.e. vocabulary that has no analogues in another culture. It in turn creates a great obstacle in communication between people of different cultures. The solution to this problem we see in the expansion of background knowledge of students. Background vocabulary is words

or expressions that have additional content and accompanying semantic or stylistic shades that are superimposed on its main meaning, known to speakers and listeners belonging to a given language culture. Therefore, an important step in learning to communicate is to familiarize students with the realities, traditions and customs of English-speaking countries. In our University in the course of learning a foreign language a lot of attention is paid to the elements of linguistic studies. If earlier country information accompanied the basic course of a foreign language only as a comment in the study of a material, now the linguistic-cultural aspect is an integral part of the lessons of a foreign language, as there is an increasing need to teach what 'lies behind the language', i.e. the culture of the country of the target language.

Conclusions and recommendations

There is no significant difference between the male and female students' opinions on the problems encountered in English teaching and learning. It also shows that there is no significant difference between the students' problem perceptions according to gender variable. Nevertheless, there are no significant differences between the students' opinions on the problems encountered in English teaching and learning according to studying in public or private secondary school, parents' occupation, family income, taking/or not English courses, the place and the duration of the subsidiary course variables. However, the higher grade levels and higher number of siblings are there, the students' perceptions on the problems encountered in English teaching and learning also rise.

The following suggestions can be made for the research results and future studies: 1- Teachers should be given competences for

taking into account the affective characteristics of students and teaching in this context in the process of learning a foreign language. 2- What kind of

renovations can be done in English teacher education programs should be put forward.

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